

**TEACHER STRESS IN RELATION TO TEACHER MOTIVATION
AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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ABSTRACT

The present study was examined on the relationship between teacher stress and teacher motivation among secondary school teachers. Teacher stress can be viewed in a number of different ways and has been described as most in precise work in the scientific dictionary. The analysis of various definitions revealed that it is a response syndrome of negative effects like anger, anxiety or depression which threatens self esteem or well being, operate as a response of negative effect resulting an imbalance or discrepancy between the demands made and the ability to cope with them. Teacher motivation is the factors influencing the teacher in class room teaching, school administration, professional pleasure, climatic factors, interpersonal relations, student behaviour, working conditions, professional development and personal aspects. The data collected from 210 teachers from 35 selected secondary schools by using two standardized questionnaires namely 'Stress creators in teaching scale' developed by (Indira, 1996) and 'The teacher motivation scale' developed by Undurty (1988). The data was analyzed with the help of statistical analyses by using Means, Standard Deviations, Critical ratios and Correlations. The results of study are male and female teachers experience moderate stress and average motivation. Teacher stress and teacher motivation were influenced in their locality, age and designation. More experienced teachers have less stress and high motivation.

Keywords : Teacher Stress, Teacher Motivation, class room teaching, school administration, professional pleasure, climatic factors, interpersonal relations, student behaviour, working conditions, professional development and personal aspects.

Introduction

Stress is a term used to designate a wide range of man's arising in response to various extreme effects. The work is broadly used to designate non specific body responses to any un-favourable effect. In attempting to satisfy the needs, an individual may have to face failure sometimes. When an individual effort in satisfying a need is thwarted, he is subjected to a number of stresses. Frustration, anxiety, conflicts or pressurizes may cause stress. A mentally healthy person will have a few occasions of stressful situation, which he will beet successfully.

Selye (1956), an endocrinologist, perceived stress to be a neural physiological phenomenon. More

specifically he defined it as a general adaptive syndrome or non-specific response to demands placed upon the human body. These demands could either stimulate or threaten the individual. The term has been further defined by Gold and Roth (1993), "a condition of disequilibria within the intellectual, emotional and physical state of the individual; it is generated by one's perceptions of a situation, which result in physical and emotional reactions. It can be either positive or negative, depending upon one's interpretation.

Motivation is an inner state of mind or aroused feeling generated through basic needs or drives which compel an individual to respond by creating a kind of tension or urge to act. It is a preparation for responding in

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some selective manner for the satisfaction of the related need and it is a goal directed activity, pursued till the attainment of goal. A change in goal may bring about changes in the nature and strength of the motive, while attainment of the goal helps in the release of tension aroused by a specific motive. Motivation may be considered to be a learned response or tendency and also an innate disposition.

Rosen, Fox and Gregory (1972) defined motivation as a readiness or disposition to respond in some ways and not others to a variety of situations. Carroll (1969) defined motivation is a rather specific process which has been learned. It is directed towards a goal. Srivastava et al (2002) examined the relationship between job and life stress and health outcomes of management personnel. Job stress was significantly related to physical health complaints (PHC) and pathogenic health habits (PHH). As compared to job stress, life stress was found to be a stronger predictor of health outcomes. Life stress was significantly related to higher systolic BP, PHC and PHH.

Mittal Jaiprakash (1997) studied on teachers' motivation to work and some factors associated with high and low work motivation of teachers. He concluded that high and low motivated teachers differed along the following personality variables respectively Low vs. High anxiety, extraversion vs. introversion, and tender minded emotionality vs. alert poise and independence vs. Subdued. The teachers' motivation to work was significantly related to job satisfaction. Those higher on work motivation perceived organizational climate to be characterized by less disengagement and alienation, more spirit, more openness and autonomy than those low on the same.

Bhattacharya (2000) established that intrinsic motivation is essential for elevating level of teaching competency and improving attitude towards teaching profession of primary teachers.

Objectives of the study :

- To study the stress among the secondary school teachers gender, locality, qualifications, designation, age, experience, medium of instruction, marital status and type of management

variables.

- To study the motivation among the secondary school teachers gender, locality, qualifications, designation, age, experience, medium of instruction, marital status and type of management variables.
- To study the relationship between stress and motivation of secondary school teachers.

Hypotheses :

- There are no significant differences between the stress of secondary school teachers considered under gender, locality, qualifications, designation, age, experience, medium of instruction, marital status and type of management variables.
- There are no significant differences between the motivation of secondary school teachers under gender, locality, qualifications, designation, age, experience, medium of instruction, marital status and type of management variables.
- There is no significant relationship between stress and motivation of secondary school teachers.

METHOD

Sample of respondents

The study was conducted on a sample of 210 teachers from selected secondary schools from Vizianagaram district of Andhra Pradesh. The sample consists of gender (126 Male and 84 female), locality (114 Rural and 96 urban), qualifications (80 D.Ed, 88 B.Ed and 42 M.Ed), designation (103 School Assistants and 107 Secondary grade teachers), age (123 below 35 yrs and 87 above 35 yrs), Experience (115 Below 15 yrs and 95 above 15 yrs), medium of instruction (92 English and 118 Telugu), marital status (157 married and 53 unmarried) and type of management (47 Zilla parished, 36 government, 46 residential, 35 municipal and 46 minority teachers). The data were collected by way of randomized sampling technique. Thus the total sample of 210 was adequate to test the hypotheses in the above mentioned variables.

Tools

Keeping in the view of the objective of the study and also the nature of research, the standardized tools 'Stress creators in teaching scale' developed by Indira

(1996) and 'The teacher motivation scale' developed by Undurty (1988) were used for the present study

Procedure

Stress creators in teaching scale developed by Indira (1996) and the teacher motivation scale developed by Undurty (1988) were selected to suit the specific needs of the present study as well as the sample to be investigated. The researcher approached the various Headmasters of the secondary schools and got the permission from ten schools. The preliminary

information sheet, Stress creators in teaching scale and the teacher motivation scale were given to teachers and they were asked to fill the preliminary information and both the scales as per the instructions given in the scales.

Statistical analysis

To measure the significant difference between the two dimensions of each demographical variable, means, standard deviations, critical ratio and correlation values are computed. The scores were analyzed with the help of computer and used SPSS package for analysing the data

Results and Discussion :

Table: 1
The comparison across different variables in Teacher stress

SI. No	Category	N	Mean	S.D	C.R- values									
1	<u>GENDER</u>													
	Male	126	93.24	17.23	2.22*									
	Female	84	98.86	18.49										
2	<u>LOCALITY</u>													
	Rural	114	94.72	17.25	2.61*									
	Urban	96	88.26	18.32										
3	<u>QUALIFICATIONS</u>													
	D.Ed	80	89.45	18.37	<table border="1"> <tr> <td></td> <td>B.Ed</td> <td>M.Ed</td> </tr> <tr> <td>D.ED</td> <td>1.91@</td> <td>0.64@</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B.Ed</td> <td></td> <td>0.88@</td> </tr> </table>		B.Ed	M.Ed	D.ED	1.91@	0.64@	B.Ed		0.88@
		B.Ed	M.Ed											
	D.ED	1.91@	0.64@											
B.Ed		0.88@												
B.Ed	88	94.87	18.39											
M.Ed	42	91.76	19.11											
4	<u>DESIGNATION</u>													
	School assistants	103	95.45	17.21	2.09*									
Secondary grade	107	90.48	17.13											
5	<u>AGE</u>													
	Below 35 yrs	123	94.62	17.69	1.80@									
Above 35 yrs	87	90.04	18.48											
6	<u>EXPERIENCE</u>													
	Below 15 yrs	115	95.47	17.25	2.54*									
Above 15 yrs	95	89.11	18.79											
7	<u>MEDIUM</u>													
	English	92	90.62	18.93	2.42*									
Telugu	118	96.83	17.76											

8	<u>MARITAL STATUS</u>	157	90.62	17.19	1.70@				
	Married	53	95.57	18.65					
	Unmarried								
9	<u>TYPE OF MANAGEMENT</u>	47	88.51	18.74		Govt.	Residential	Municipal	Minority
	Zillah parished	36	91.44	19.09	Zilla	0.60@	1.86@	0.29@	0.55@
	Government	46	95.76	18.79	parish.				
	Residential	35	89.76	19.16	Govt.		1.02@	0.37@	0.18@
	Municipal	46	90.65	18.81	Residential			1.40@	1.30@
	Minority				Municipal				0.20@

@ Not Significant * Significant at 0.05 level ** significant at 0.01 level

The means, standard deviations and critical ratios of gender, locality, qualifications, designation, age, experience, medium of instruction, marital status and type of management related to the teacher stress were incorporated in Table: 1. It is evident that significant differences were found between male and female, rural and urban, school assistants and secondary grade

teachers, below 15 yrs and above 15 yrs experienced teachers and English and Telugu medium teachers in their stress. So the null hypotheses framed on these comparisons were rejected. The mean differences between all other comparisons were not differed significantly in their stress. So the null hypotheses framed on these comparisons were accepted.

Table: 2
The comparison across different variables in Teacher motivation

SI. No	Category	N	Mean	S.D	C.R- values		
1	<u>GENDER</u>						
	Male	126	113.65	27.23	3.00**		
	Female	84	126.17	31.19			
2	<u>LOCALITY</u>						
	Rural	114	100.21	28.25	5.60**		
	Urban	96	118.32	18.32			
3	<u>QUALIFICATIONS</u>					B.Ed	M.Ed
	D.Ed	80	110.61	20.47			
	B.Ed	88	116.87	19.19	D.Ed	2.04*	1.89@
	M.Ed	42	102.81	22.13	B.Ed		3.53**

** P<0.01

The total scores of 210 Teacher's Stress and Teacher's motivation relationship value was tabulated in table: 3. It can be observed that the value is positive and significant. So the null hypothesis is rejected and there is a significant relationship between Teacher Stress and Teacher motivation.

Conclusion

Both male and female teachers experience moderate stress and average motivation. Teacher stress and teacher motivation were influenced in their locality. Teacher stress was not influenced by qualifications but teachers' motivation was influenced by qualifications. Teachers stress and teacher motivation were influenced by age. Teacher stress and teacher motivation were influenced in their designation. More experienced teachers have less stress and high motivation. Teachers' stress is influenced by medium of instruction but teacher motivation is not influenced by marital status. Teachers' stress is not influenced by marital status but teacher motivation is influenced by marital status. Teachers' stress is not influenced by type of management and teacher motivation is influenced by type of management. There is a significant and highly positive relationship between Teacher Stress and Teacher motivation.

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